

ETIOLOGICAL SPECTRUM OF ADULT PATIENTS PRESENTING WITH STATUS EPILEPTICUS

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ABSTRACT

Background: Status epilepticus (SE) is one of the most critical neurological emergencies with significant morbidity and mortality. Its prevalence and clinical characteristics vary globally due to regional healthcare access, comorbidities, and precipitating factors. In developing nations like Nepal, there are limited data reported on Status Epilepticus presentation, etiologies and outcomes. **Methods:** A hospital-based, observational, cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted at Nobel Medical College Teaching Hospital, Biratnagar, from July 2022 to June 2024. Ninety-six consecutive adult patients (≥ 18 years) diagnosed with SE were included based on International League Against Epilepsy (ILAE) criteria. Sociodemographic characteristics, clinical findings, laboratory parameters, neuroimaging, and electroencephalography (EEG) results were analyzed using SPSS v16. **Results:** The mean age of patients was 46.1 ± 18 years, with a male predominance (58.4%). Common comorbidities were epilepsy (28.1%), hypertension (21.9%), and diabetes mellitus (19.8%). History of substance use was present in 48.9%. Generalized convulsive Status Epilepticus (GCSE) accounted for 51% of cases and Nonconvulsive Status Epilepticus (NCSE) was observed in 19% cases. Stroke (21.9%) and central nervous system infections (20.8%) were leading etiologies. Abnormal EEG was observed in 23.9% cases, and abnormal neuroimaging was found in 34.4% cases. The most frequent complications were physical injuries (30.2%) and aspiration pneumonia with hypoxia (22.9%). Refractory Status Epilepticus occurred in 21.9% of cases and super-refractory Status Epilepticus was observed in 9.4%. Mortality was 8.3% and recurrence during hospitalization was seen in 11.4%. **Conclusion:** Status Epilepticus was more common in non-epileptic adults without prior history of seizure, predominantly presenting as generalized convulsive Status Epilepticus. Stroke was the most common etiology, followed by Central Nervous System infections and alcohol withdrawal seizure. Most patients had favorable clinical outcomes with appropriate management, though mortality and recurrence rates remained clinically significant.

KEYWORDS: Status epilepticus, seizure, epilepsy, stroke.

INTRODUCTION

Status epilepticus (SE) is defined as a failure of seizure termination mechanisms or initiation of prolonged epileptic activity leading to continuous or recurrent seizures without recovery between episodes.^[1] SE can cause neuronal injury, altered neuronal networks, and long-term functional deficits if not treated early. The operational definition of SE includes continuous seizure activity lasting ≥ 5 minutes for generalized tonic-clonic seizures, requiring emergency treatment.^[2]

The annual global incidence of SE is 10 to 41 per 100,000 population, with higher rates in developing countries.^[3-5] SE contributes to approximately 0.07% of hospital admissions in high-income countries, but data from low-resource settings are inadequate.^[6] The burden of SE is beyond acute management, often leading to prolonged hospitalization, neurological disability, and socioeconomic burden, particularly in resource-limited healthcare systems such as Nepal.

Etiologies of SE differ with age. In adults, stroke, metabolic disturbances, infections, and poor antiepileptic

drug (AED) adherence are common triggers.^[7-9] In older adults, cerebrovascular diseases predominate, while in younger populations, infectious and metabolic etiologies are more common.^[10-12] Convulsive SE are clinically diagnosed but Nonconvulsive SE (NCSE), often underdiagnosed, requires continuous EEG (cEEG) monitoring for detection.^[13,14]

Neuroimaging is helpful to identify underlying etiologies and also detect seizure-related cortical abnormalities, while EEG provides confirmation and guides in management.^[15-17] First-line treatment of SE includes benzodiazepines, followed by AEDs such as phenytoin, valproate, and levetiracetam.^[18,19] Refractory SE, which is resistant to first- and second-line agents, may require anesthetic agents, though their use is associated to increased morbidity.^[20]

Given the limited data from South East Asia, this study aims to describe the clinical and epidemiological profile of adult SE patients in a tertiary hospital in Nepal. This study will help to plan management strategies and identify local etiological patterns.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This was a descriptive, cross-sectional hospital-based study conducted at the Department of Neurology, Nobel Medical College Teaching Hospital, Biratnagar, Nepal, over two years (July 2022–June 2024). Adult patients (≥ 18 years) presenting with SE to the emergency department, neurology ward, intensive care unit (ICU), or general ward were included after obtaining informed consent. Status epilepticus in this study was defined according to established clinical and electroencephalographic criteria. Convulsive status epilepticus was defined, as per the International League Against Epilepsy, as a generalized tonic–clonic seizure lasting more than 5 minutes, or focal onset or absence

seizures lasting more than 10 minutes, with or without impaired consciousness, or the occurrence of two or more seizures within a 5-minute period, without return to baseline consciousness between episodes. Non-convulsive status epilepticus was defined based on the Salzburg Consensus Criteria. In patients without known epileptic encephalopathy, it's defined as presence of epileptiform discharges greater than 2.5 Hz on EEG, or discharges ≤ 2.5 Hz or rhythmic delta/theta activity greater than 0.5 Hz along with at least one of the following: clinical and EEG improvement after intravenous antiepileptic drug administration, subtle ictal clinical phenomena, or typical spatiotemporal evolution. In patients with known epileptic encephalopathy, non-convulsive status epilepticus was defined by an increase in the voltage and frequency of epileptiform discharges on EEG with associated clinical improvement, or by improvement in both clinical and EEG features following intravenous antiepileptic drug administration.

Data Collection

An informed verbal or written consent was taken. The study protocol was submitted for ethical approval to institutional ethical review board. Clinical data included age, sex, comorbidities, etiologies, precipitating factors, EEG, neuroimaging, and laboratory results. Patients were observed for complications, response to treatment, recurrence, and outcomes during hospital stay

RESULTS

Demographics and Comorbidities

Of 96 patients, 56 were male (58.4%) and 40 female (41.6%). The mean age was 46.1 ± 18 years, with most patients (64.5%) between 18–39 years. Common comorbidities included epilepsy (28.1%), hypertension (21.9%), and diabetes mellitus (19.8%). Substance use (alcohol, tobacco, or both) was reported in 48.9%.

Table 1: Baseline Demographic Characteristics of study participants (N=96)

Characteristics	Categories	Number of Patients	Percentage
Age group in years	18-39	62	64.5
	40-59	27	28.1
	60-79	7	7.3
Mean Age in years(\pm SD)			46.1 \pm 18
Gender	Female	40	41.6
	Male	56	58.4
Comorbidities	Diabetes	19	19.8
	Hypertension	21	21.9
	Epilepsy	27	28.1
	Psychiatric comorbidities	5	5.2
Substance use	Alcohol	27	28.1
	Smoking	20	20.8
	Other	2	2.1

Clinical Presentations

Generalized convulsive SE (GCSE) was the most common presentation (51%), followed by NCSE with coma (19%). Other forms included focal to bilateral

convulsive SE (2%), Epilepsia partialis continua (4%), and myoclonic SE (1%). Approximately 23% of patients presented with SE of unknown onset.

Figure 1: Clinical Semiology of study participants (N=96)

Etiologies

Stroke (21.9%) and central nervous system infections (20.8%) were the leading etiologies. Alcohol withdrawal (18.8%), AED noncompliance (17.7%), and hyponatremia (9.4%) were also common triggers.

Abnormal neuroimaging was found in 34.4%, predominantly stroke-related lesions. EEG abnormalities were observed in 23.9%, primarily generalized or focal epileptiform discharges. CSF abnormalities suggestive of infection were present in 20.8%.

Figure 2: Etiological spectrum among study participants (N=96)

Treatment Response and Outcomes

Most patients (68.8%) responded to first- or second-line AEDs. Refractory SE occurred in 21.9%, while 9.4% were super-refractory. Physical injuries (30.2%) and aspiration pneumonia with hypoxia (22.9%) were

common complications. Mortality occurred in eight patients (8.3%). Recurrence during hospitalization was observed in 11.4%. Around 18.7% of cases had ICU stay of more than 10 days.

Table 2: Complications among study participants (N=96).

Complications	Number of patients	Percentage
Cerebral edema	7	7.3
Aspiration Pneumonia	22	22.9
Hypoxia/ Respiratory failure	22	22.9
Cardiac arrhythmia	3	3.1
Hypoglycemia	3	3.1
Hyperkalemia	7	7.3
Multi organ failure	5	5.2
Renal failure	7	7.3
Physical injury	29	30.2

DISCUSSION

This study gives insight into the clinico-epidemiological aspects and etiological spectrum of SE among adults in a tertiary care setting in eastern Nepal. The mean age of 46 years indicates SE affects a younger population compared to Western data, where incidence is high in elderly population.^[5] The male predominance in this study is associated with increased exposure to SE risk factors such as trauma, alcohol, and stroke. Cerebrovascular disease was the leading etiology (21.9%), which is consistent with other studies identifying stroke as the predominant cause in adults.^[21] In contrast, the high proportion of CNS infections (20.8%) reflects regional epidemiology. Various CNS infections including post-infectious encephalitis and neurocysticercosis are more prevalent in South Asian countries. Alcohol withdrawal (18.8%) and AED noncompliance were also significant factors. GCSE was the most frequent presentation (51%), followed by NCSE (19%). The lower NCSE detection rate may reflect the limited availability of continuous EEG monitoring in Nepal, which can underestimate the true prevalence of NCSE. Early identification and management are crucial, as delayed detection of NCSE is associated with worse neurological outcomes. EEG abnormalities were observed in 24% of cases which was lower than reported in studies using continuous EEG (40–50%).^[22] Similarly, MRI and CT abnormalities were noted in 34%, which were consistent with structural causes such as stroke or CNS infections. The relatively low proportion of abnormal imaging in metabolic or infectious etiologies supports prior findings that many SE patients can have normal structural imaging.^[23] In our study most patients responded to standard first- and second-line AED therapy. However, refractory and super-refractory SE accounted for approximately one-third of cases, which was consistent with global data.^[24] Mortality (8.3%) in this study was lower than previously reported rates (16–20%)^[25], likely reflecting early intervention and the younger patient population. The recurrence rate of 11.4% during hospitalization indicates the need for follow-up care and adherence counseling. Studies from other

developing countries show similar etiological pattern but higher mortality. This indicates the potential benefits of early management and improved critical care facilities. The present study has shown stroke, infections, and alcohol withdrawal as major causes which are preventable. This reflects the need for community-based prevention programs.

CONCLUSION

Status epilepticus in Nepal predominantly affects younger adults. It is more common in males without prior history of epilepsy. The most frequent subtype was generalized convulsive SE and major causes were stroke, infections, and alcohol withdrawal. Although most patients responded well to conventional therapy, refractory cases and associated complications were significant to morbidity and mortality. Improved diagnostic availability, particularly continuous EEG, and early intervention protocols could further change the outcomes in resource-limited settings.

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